

Design of Double Arm Motorcycle Swing Arm Using Topology Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on designing a double-arm swing arm for two-wheeled electric motorcycles used in track racing at around 100 kmph, which would experience immense multi-axial loading. Previous researchers have focused on high-performance applications involving speeds to and beyond 200 kmph with the following limitations: Complex geometry, increased weight, and increased cost. We see that lower speed, lower power, and lower curb mass applications are not optimized in such designs. In this paper, the focus is given to simpler geometry, lower mass, and lower speed band optimization. The swingarm was designed in Fusion 360 using topology optimization and tested in Ansys Workbench. It was seen that with a simple rectangular geometry a 22% increment in comparison to OEM swing arms which generally weigh 10 Kg, have a minimum FOS of 4.48, max stress of 63.4 MPa, max strain of 8.7×10^{-4} , a maximum displacement of 1.5mm, max shear stress of 16.67MPa and fatigue life of 10^8 cycles all of which comply within standards mentioned by Vittore Cossalter and Tony Foale which are considered the industry standard.

Keywords: - *Swing Arm, Topology Optimization, Factor of Safety, Fusion 360, ANSYS.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Motorcycles are one of the most common modes of transport in the world. Two-wheeled electric vehicles (EVs) are on the rise to reduce carbon emissions from combustion of fossil fuels. The surge in demand for EVs led to the rise of EVs in motorsports such as Formula E and MotoE. This led to an urgent innovation in the vehicles' performance in the fields of battery technology, drivetrain, aerodynamics, and structure. In the field of motorsports, innovation led to improved track performance by increasing the range, reducing battery size, re-designing the structure (chassis) for a lower center of gravity, and improving aerodynamics by altering the shape of the battery. The material used for the chassis and other parts attached to it have been researched upon extensively for improved characteristics of stress, strain, torsional rigidity, weight, deformation, and fatigue. In the field of motorsports, expensive materials may be used to achieve improved performance, however, in the commuter segment, these expensive materials cannot be used due to the high cost involved hence providing an EV at a cost-effective price by the use of normal available materials plays a crucial role in decreasing cost.

The chassis of the vehicle is connected to the front forks and the handlebar, the subframe at the rear, and also the swing arm. The swing arm connects to the rear wheel and the rear suspension. The swingarm is traditionally a symmetrical pair of arms usually made in pairs of parallel pipes connecting the axle and the main frame (chassis). The swing arm must handle the loads from the rear tires showing adequate stiffness response. The undulations on the road, the forces acting on the swingarm due to acceleration and deceleration of the vehicle, and the unequal forces acting due to cornering of the vehicle while transmitting these forces onto the chassis. Hence the weight of the swing arm plays a primary role in the behaviour of the motorcycle. The reduced weight of the swing arm will increase the overall performance by reducing the stress and the strain acting on it. The swingarms are generally made of steel, aluminium, and magnesium. Aluminium alloys are largely used in MotoGP and MotoE due to the lower weight. However, aluminium is a softer metal than steel, hence it requires heat treatment processes to improve its hardness.

Several methods are used to improve the performance of the swingarm such as: Generative design, intuitive methods, and evolutionary methods. Generative design requires extensive pre-processing and base models to improve upon targeted characteristics, intuitive methods are unable to perform under complex loading and constraints, and evolutionary methods suffer from mesh dependencies. Due to these limitations, an alternate method called topology optimization is used, the only limitation of this is that the design outputs are complex and require manual constraints. The design of a swingarm involves working with Finite Element Analysis tools to perform structural analysis. Usually, designs are improved manually using a trial-and-error method through shaping and sizing, which is time-consuming and leaves a margin for improvement.

Topology optimization is an innovative mathematical method-based tool used to enhance the performance of a design while operating under constraints. It analyses the material within the boundary conditions and constraints to optimize performance by using a density-based approach for solving material distribution problems. This method is

used in aerospace, automotive, and biomedical engineering applications. To manage complex design output, an iterative method where each iteration acts as a surrogate for the next allowing control over design complexity.

2 Background

A study was conducted on the swing arms of three World Superbike Championship bikes aimed at linking data such as stiffness and natural frequency. The data was analyzed and collected from both experimental and CAD FEA models. (Risitano et al., 2012)

Another research carried out by (Patil et al., 2008) indicated that the stiffness of the swingarm played a critical role in the stability and response of the motorcycle. The stiffness of the swingarm was determined by the FEA method. It was observed that the single arm had a significant weight reduction compared to the double arm while providing better stiffness. (Vittore Cossalter, 1997) stated that the swingarm must undergo deformation to maintain the slip angle of the tires ensuring maximum traction through corners. The ideal range is stated to be 1 to 2 kN/mm.

An investigation was conducted using materials aluminium 6061 T6 alloy and AISI 4340 steel. For an iterative swing arm design. Two designs were produced from the initial design, one being Aluminium 6061 T6 alloy and the other being AISI 4340 steel. The results showed that the AISI 4340 design showed 3.3 times more lateral stiffness and 1.36 times more torsional stiffness in comparison to the aluminium design although the Aluminium design was 33% lighter than the AISI 4340 design. (Swathikrishnan S et al., 2019)

Another study was performed on the design of a carbon fibre swingarm. The Finite element analysis was performed, and the stiffness was experimentally measured in vertical and horizontal directions. The maximum observed strain was found to be lower than the allowable maximum stress indicating sufficient strength of the swingarm. The final carbon fibre prototype was found to be 29% lighter than the aluminium counterpart. The deviation between the experimental and numerical results was found to be 4% and 28% for vertical and horizontal stiffness respectively. (Smith & Kienhöfer, 2014)

(Cassani & Mancuso Ducati Motor Holding SpA, 2005), performed a numerical-experimental design approach in the development of a Ducati Monster S4R swing arm. The design was analyzed numerically in a loading condition with a maximum bending moment and solved using a matrix structural analysis with the component idealized as a beam. An experimental study was performed including the Leyni test and bump test. The truss-based design proved to be effective against bending moments without an increase in mass.

The stability of a motorcycle due to the deformation of the swingarm was studied at a low-frequency mode ranging from 1-4Hz. The results of the studies proved to show that the deformability of the swing arm had minimal effect on the stability of SuperSport motorcycles. (Taraborrelli et al., 2017)

(K. Satyanarayana et al., 2020) designed and analyzed a motorcycle swing arm with AISI 1020 and Aluminium 7075 using SolidWorks and Ansys. Deformation, stress, weight, factor of safety, and fatigue life were compared under dynamic loading conditions with different materials. The Results showed that Aluminium 7075 had a lower deformation of .0096692 mm compared to .33345 mm of AISI 1020. The stresses developed in both materials were comparable at 44.132 MPa for AISI 1020 and 45.046 MPa for Aluminium 7075. The aluminium design had a much lower mass of 3.506 Kg compared to AISI 1020 at 9.78981 Kg. Hence the study concluded that Aluminium 7075 was the optimal material for the swing arm design.

An analysis of a case-hardened mild steel swing arm was performed. The CAD model was developed in Catia V5, meshed in Hypermesh 12.0, and solved in Ansys 15.0 showing that the response of the swingarm for modal loads ranging from 45.62 to 90.83 Hz showed displacement range from .000922 mm to .003976 mm respectively. (V.S Dixit et al., 2016)

(Balasubramanian et al., 2021) explored the prospect of utilizing generative design to model a single-sided swingarm. The generative study was performed in Fusion 360 with Aluminium 6061 T6 alloy and Aluminium 7075 T6 alloy as the materials of choice. The analysis of the mechanical properties of the materials concluded that Aluminium 6061 T6 alloy was superior in performance. The results of the analysis were observed with the Von Mises stress at 99.1 MPa, the minimum safety factor at 2.77, and the maximum displacement being .63 mm. The mass of the design was 2.9 Kg.

(Rohithkumar et al., 2021) used generative design tools to optimize the swingarm. The CAD model was developed in Fusion 360 and optimized within Fusion 360 using the generative design workspace. The material choice in the study is Aluminium 6061 T6 alloy. The results of the study displayed a 49% mass reduction with the final design at 1.37 Kg, a safety factor of 1.37, a .03 mm deformation, and a maximum equivalent stress of 199.79 MPa.

Iwasaki et al (2004), performed a study on the design and development of a magnesium swing arm. Magnesium was chosen as the material of choice due to its light weight, AZ31 and AZ61 alloy plates were welded together to produce the part. The study resulted in a swing arm with a 10% reduction in mass and a 60% increase in torsional rigidity compared to an aluminium counterpart, and the static and fatigue strength of the welded joints were clarified. (Iwasaki et al., 2004)

(Dragoni & Forestit, 1998), designed and numerically analyzed the performance of carbon fibre composite swing arm. The model was evaluated on the ALGOR Hypersap finite element package, and the final prototype involved magnesium and aluminium inserts to support a low inertia. The results of the study exhibited a 10% increase in torsional stiffness, 30% mass reduction, and 40% decrease in moment of inertia in comparison to its magnesium counterpart.

Odom et al (1982), explored the concept of a composite swing arm with a steel core. The prototype displayed a 53% weight reduction in comparison to the steel counterpart, the stress induced was comparable to that of the steel

counterpart, and the stiffness showed a 23% decrease with respect to its steel counterpart. (E.M Odom & D.F. Adams, 1982)

According to a study by Powar et al (2016), the weight of a motorcycle swing arm was optimized. The optimized swing arm weighed 1.8 kg whereas the surrogate swing arm weighed in at 3.2 kg. The final design maintained acceptable stress under loading, proving to be a feasible design for weight reduction. Overall, a weight reduction of 44% was achieved. (Powar et al., 2016)

(Hemanth Kumar et al., 2023) Topology optimization proves superior capability in comparison to conventional size, shape, and global optimization techniques. The method is independent of design variables and operates with a greater design space and convergence rate. Topology optimization serves as a means for an all-around improvement of a design development, it leads to increased performance, reduced mass, and an increase in manufacturing efficiency leading to lower time and lower cost. (Shanmugasundar et al., 2020)

(Hassaan Abdullah et al., 2018) further optimized a Honda RC213V specified for MotoGP by employing an optimization technique called shape optimization. The optimization was made on the basis of a multi-axial load analysis carried out in a swingarm CAD model. Without compromising the safety factor, it has been observed that a 15% reduction in total weight has been achieved.

Sonawane (2021) optimized a Yamaha R1M MotoGP bike swing arm by employing shape optimization. The optimization was performed based on multi-axial loads. The research shows a decrease in mass and safety factors with an increase in deformation. (Rushikesh Atmaram Sonawane, 2021)

The authors utilized topology optimization to refine a front wheel. The material of choice is Aluminium 7075 alloy, the numerical analysis was performed for a braking condition with a simple static loading of maximum tyre pressure and equivalent bearing. The study resulted in a mass decrease from 3.36 Kg to 2.54 Kg. (Yesane et al., 2016).

(Rankhambe & Kumar Nhaichaniya, 2017), utilized topology optimization tools to reduce the weight of a swingarm. The design was modelled in Catia V5. The condition simulated for was a cornering condition with a 70% of the load on the inner arm and a 30% load on the outer arm. The results of the study displayed up to 50% in mass reduction with the initial model weighing in at 11.2 Kg and the final model at 5.8 Kg

3 Design and Development

The design and development of the swing arm is described as multiple sub-sections Section 3.1 details the choice of the material through comparison of key factors such as density, tensile strength, and yield strength. Section 3.2 covers the method used to optimize. Section 3.3 covers the vehicle parameters, and section 3.4 covers the formulas needed to determine the load characteristics.

3.1 Material Properties

The material properties of a load-bearing part such as the swing arm must be taken into consideration. The material must have the ability to bear the load and stress during multi-axial loading scenarios while also being light to ensure maximum performance. Unique to track-purpose motorcycles, the swing arm must be designed to deform within set limits to ensure maximum grip by the tires.

Table 1: Comparison of Material Properties: AL6061, AL7075, and SS430

Parameters	Aluminium 6061 T6	Aluminium 7075 T6	Stainless Steel 4310
Density	2.7 g/cm ³	2.81g/cm ³	7.86g/cm ³
Ultimate tensile strength	310 MPa	572 MPa	670 MPa
Yield Strength	276 MPa	503 MPa	435 MPa
Youngs Modulus	68.9 GPa	71.7GPa	205 GPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.33	0.33	.29
Elongation at Break	17%	11%	25.5%

Inferring from the table 1, Aluminium 6061 T6 alloy (What Advantage Does Aluminium Alloy Swing Arm Have to Change, n.d.) is being used in this design as it has a density 65% lighter than Stainless steel, a Poisson's ratio 13% greater than stainless steel and elongation at break 6% greater than Aluminium 7075 T6. The material proves to have a good balance between all key factors making it optimal for this study.

3.2 Design Methodology

Fig 1: Design Methodology

The methodology followed in this study starts with a primordial CAD model of the swing arm under the required parameters. Once a CAD is made topology optimization is performed with the maximum loading scenario. The refined mesh results can be used to optimize the design geometry. This process can be repeated till a required reduction in mass is achieved. Once the mass target is achieved, the design undergoes further analysis for validation under factors such as stress, strain, and deformation. The design is finalized if the factor of safety is acceptable.

3.3 Motorcycle Specifications

Table 2: Motorcycle Specifications

Parameter	Specification
Kerb Weight	100 kg
Wheelbase	1.38 m
Ground Clearance	.1 m
Power	20 KW
Top Speed	110 Km/h

3.4 Simulation Scenarios

During the course of a race, the swing arm undergoes multi-axial loading. These loads are the most prominent during braking and cornering. The cornering loading scenario is being considered for this research.

During a cornering scenario, the motorcycle's Center of Gravity shifts laterally with respect to the cornering radius and lean angle (Tony Foale, 2002). In addition to the shift in the center of gravity, the swing arm is subjected to an equilibrium load from the rear tire despite the centrifugal and centripetal forces balancing each other out. Utilizing the data from Table 2.

$$W_R = \frac{\frac{1}{2} * m * g * a_2}{L} - \frac{\frac{1}{2} * m * g * h}{L * g} * a * \cos \theta$$

Braking Scenario

Where,

m = mass of the vehicle

g = acceleration due to gravity

a = acceleration of the vehicle (0.5g)

L = Wheelbase

h = C.G. Height

a_2 = longitudinal distance between C.G. and Rear wheel centre

θ = Lean angle

$$(m * g * L' + C.G_{height} * m * a) * \cos \theta = W_T * L'$$

Cornering Formula

W_T = Load acting on the swingarm

L' = Shift in centre of gravity (lateral direction)

θ = Lean angle

$$W_C = \frac{m * v^2}{r}$$

Radial Forces Formula

v = velocity of the motorcycle

r = radius of curvature

m = mass of the motorcycle

4 Simulation and Optimization

The topology optimization is carried out within Fusion 360 (Fusion 360 | Autodesk, n.d.) enabling faster changes to the model. Further Simulations were carried out using Ansys Mechanical Workbench (Ansys n.d.) as it provides information about stressed regions and has additional tools such as fatigue loading, which was also tested and simulated for.

4.1 Topology Optimization Setup

The main forces acting on the swing arm at a 30-degree lean angle and 40 m turn radius are W_c , W_t , W_r which have the following values:

$$W_c = 1125 \text{ N}$$

$$W_t = 2327 \text{ N}$$

$$W_e = 380 \text{ N}$$

The optimization setup involved constraining the swingarm pivot with a revolute joint and rigidly constraining the spring joint. The load W_c is the radial load applied to the rear axle mount outward on each side. The load W_t , is the cornering load experienced normal to the arms of the swing arm at the point of the axle with one acting normally up and one normally down with respect to the swing arm. The load W_e is experienced by the underside of the swingarm experienced due to the chain tension. The optimization study was performed with a target mass of 60%.

4.2 Topology Analysis

The current design was optimized in fusion 360. The bolt point was constrained as a pin joint while the spring mounting point was constrained as a fixed joint. A targeted mass of 50% is the given criteria.

Fig 4: Final design

4.3 Structural Analysis

The final design was validated using ANSYS Workbench. Stress, strain, displacement, shear stress, fatigue loading, and factor of safety calculations were performed on the design. These tests were carried out to confirm that the design satisfied the necessary performance parameters and could sustain the anticipated loads and operating conditions. The setup involved the same loading scenario and constraints as the topology optimization study. The meshing was performed in Ansys mechanical workbench. A quadratic solver was employed to obtain the results. The findings of these analyses provided useful insights into the design's behaviour.

Fig 5: Equivalent Stress

Fig 6: Equivalent Strain

Fig 7: Safety Factor

Fig 8: Shear Stress

Fig 9: Total Deformation

Fig 10: Fatigue Life

Fig 11: Fatigue Safety Factor

Above figures 5 to 11 showcase the various property contours across the swing arm under loading. Fig 5 showcases the concentration of stress at the root of the arm with the outer end of the arm experiencing relatively lower amounts. From Fig 6 we can see that similar to Fig 5, strain concentration is at the root of the arm with the outer end having relatively lower strain. The lowest factor of safety observed in Fig 7 is also at the root of the arm. The maximum concentration of shear stress is also found at the root of the arm in Fig 8. Deformation as seen In Fig 9 is maximum at the end of the arms which is a result of the radial forces. Fatigue life contours from Fig 10 show consistent response to fatigue loading by the entirety of the arm. The factor of safety of fatigue loading shows a minimum at the root of the arm.

5 Results and Conclusion

Table 3 : Final Results

Parameter	Results
Weight	9 Kg
Max Equivalent Stress	62.39 MPa
Max Equivalent Strain	8.7×10^{-4}
Max Deformation	1.5 mm
Min Factor of Safety	4.48
Max Fatigue Life	10^8 cycles
Min Fatigue Life Factor of Safety	2.65
Max Shear Stress	16.59 MPa
Torsional Stiffness	1.5 kN/mm

As inferred from Table 3, a topology optimization tool can be used to further reduce weight and improve the performance of the swing arm. For track purposes, weight is one of the most important criteria as lighter motorcycles tend to have greater acceleration and speed, thereby establishing the foundation for further exploration into the application of the tool.

It can be concluded that the root of the arms to be crucial to the performance of the swing arm establishing itself to be a key point of interest for future research aimed at reinforcing the strength of swing arms.

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